

5G META

D1.1

Project and quality management plan

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Quality Control	2
Legal Disclaimer	2
LIST OF FIGURES	5
LIST OF TABLES	5
List of abbreviations and acronyms	6
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
1 INTRODUCTION	8
1.1 Project introduction	8
1.2 Purpose of this deliverable	8
1.3 Intended audience	9
1.4 Structure of the deliverable and its relation with other work packages/deliverables	9
1.5 Main changes from previous version	9
2 PROJECT STRUCTURE	10
2.1 Consortium	10
2.2 Work Packages	11
2.3 Organisational structure and decision making	12
2.3.1 Project management structure	12
2.3.2 Project coordination and Project Management Team	13
2.3.3 Steering Committee	15
2.3.4 Work Package Leaders	15
3 MANAGEMENT AND COMMUNICATION TOOLS	17
3.1 Task planning and tracking	17
3.2 Document editing and repository	19
3.3 Wiki for management procedures	20
3.4 Scheduling conference calls	20
3.5 Chat	20
3.6 Mail groups	20
4 MANAGEMENT PROCEDURES	22
4.1 Project Internal Procedures	22

4.1.1	Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on Project Management	22
4.1.2	Steering Committee meetings	22
4.1.3	General Tracking Meetings	23
4.1.4	Work Package and task Meetings	25
4.1.5	Conflict resolution	25
4.1.6	Self-assessment Audits	25
4.1.7	Gender balance in decision-making	26
4.1.8	Addressing Review Report recommendations	26
4.2	Reporting	28
4.2.1	Periodic and final reports	28
4.2.2	Continuous reporting	28
4.2.3	Deliverables	28
4.3	Deliverable management	30
4.3.1	Guidelines to write deliverables	30
4.3.2	Deliverable life cycle	31
4.3.2.1	Internal validation	31
4.3.2.2	Review process	31
4.3.2.3	Submission to the EC	31
4.3.2.4	Timeline	31
4.3.2.5	Deliverable status	32
4.3.3	List of Deliverables	32
4.4	Document management	35
4.4.1	Document referencing	36
4.4.2	Document Templates	36
4.4.3	Confidentiality and Dissemination Level	36
4.5	Risk Management	36
4.5.1	Objective	36
4.5.2	Risk Management Procedure	37
4.5.3	Risk register	37
4.6	Support processes	39
4.6.1	Deviation and Recovery Plan	39
5	CONCLUSIONS	41
	ANNEX 1: 5GMETA RISK REGISTER	42

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Geographical distribution of the partners of the 5GMETA consortium	11
Figure 2: Work Package structure and logic	12
Figure 3: Diagram of the Project management structure	13
Figure 4: WP3 Task board in MS Teams.	17
Figure 5: Sample task of WP3 in MS Teams.	18
Figure 6 Statistics of WP4 board in MS Teams.....	18
Figure 7: WP3 file repository.	19
Figure 8: Online edition of D1.1 in MS Teams.	19
Figure 9: Starting a WP2 conference call in Teams.	20
Figure 10: Template of first slide to be presented by each WP in General Tracking Meetings	23
Figure 11: Template of second slide to be presented by each WP in General Tracking Meetings	24
Figure 12: Template of third slide to be presented by each WP in General Tracking Meetings.....	24
Figure 13: Template of fourth slide to be presented by each WP in General Tracking Meetings.....	24
Figure 14 5GMETA procedure to address Review report comments	27
Figure 15 Review Report spreadsheet available in MS Teams	28
Figure 16: 5GMETA Risk Register stored in MS Teams.....	39
Figure 17 5GMETA Risk register's foreseen risks (part 1).....	42
Figure 18 5GMETA Risk register's foreseen risks (part 2).....	43
Figure 19 5GMETA Risk register's unforeseen risks	44
Figure 20 5GMETA Risk register's risk record	45

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: List of the partners of the 5GMETA consortium	10
Table 2: List of 5GMETA Work Packages.....	11
Table 3: Members of 5GMETA PMT.	14
Table 4: 5GMETA SC members.....	15
Table 5: 5GMETA WP leaders	16
Table 6: Schedule of SC meetings	23
Table 7: Schedule of General Tracking meetings	25
Table 8: Gender balance in 5GMETA decision making	26
Table 9: Structure of a Deliverable report	30
Table 10: Preparation and submission steps for the periodic / final reports and Project Deliverables .	31
Table 11 Report and deliverable status.....	32
Table 12 List of 5GMETA deliverables.....	32
Table 13: Structure of the Risk Register	37

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AM	Administrative Manger
CA	Consortium Agreement
DM	Data Manager
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
IM	Innovation Manager
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
PC	Project Coordinator
PMT	Project Management Team
QM	Quality Manager
SC	Steering Committee
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
TM	Technical Manager
T / TL	Task / Task Leader
WP / WPL	Work Package / Work Package Leader

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In the frame of 5GMETA, Work Package 1 has the objective of organising the project management activities. The project contains contributions from a number of partners and individual activities requiring close coordination to ensure that Project Milestones and Deliverables are satisfactorily achieved. The activities related to the management of the Project will ensure the timely execution of the work plan, the proper communication between participants, the data management for the Project, the creation of reporting and quality control structures and procedures, the representation and communication with external entities, primarily the European Commission, and all activities related to administrative and financial aspects concerning funds and budget allocation.

In particular, Task 1.1 is devoted to project management and technical coordination, and Task 1.5 is responsible for the Quality Management of the project and defining 5GMETA quality management system, including a set of methods, means and tools, as well as practical guidelines, aiming to ensure that the project work and results are of a uniform and high quality, that they meet the stated objectives and comply with the specifications set out in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

The DoA describes this deliverable as “*Handbook on project management, including best practices to be applied to coordinate partner activities, joint developments, and to define operating, quality and risk procedures*”. It describes the processes with which all partners must comply.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Project introduction

5GMETA is an H2020 project running from the 1st of September 2020 to the 31st of August 2023 and developed by a consortium of 11 partners. Cars capture and generate enormous volumes of data in real time about the driving dynamics, the environment, and the driver and passengers' activities. With greater proliferation of connected and automated mobility applications, the value of data from vehicles is becoming strategic, not only for the automotive industry, and it is not limited to the onboard systems and services. 5GMETA open platform aims to leverage car-captured data to stimulate, facilitate and feed innovative products and services with them. As a result, 5GMETA will empower the automotive ecosystem from industry players to new entrants, such as SMEs and high-tech start-ups, granting access to interoperable car-captured data according to data licenses. The access to data coming from relevant geographical regions will generate new opportunities and business models coming from valuable services, where data liability and billing will rely on accountability dashboard of dataflow subscription and volume consumption. 5GMETA expands 5G network functions to enable data monetization with a secure and private pipeline that manages data computing, dataflows according to service subscriptions and geographic queries. 5GMETA will realise demonstrators in terms of data heterogeneity, value creation and business models to ensure that the interests and requirements of third parties and new players are considered beyond traditional automotive industries. 5GMETA will focus on technology transfer activities performing different dissemination activities, tutorials and hackathons to incubators and clusters to capture the attention of SMEs and high-tech start-ups with a platform leading to new opportunities in incoming profitable markets.

1.2 Purpose of this deliverable

This deliverable is intended to be a handbook on project management, including best practices to be applied to coordinate partner activities, and joint developments, and to define operating, quality and risk procedures. To this end, it sets out and defines the 5GMETA quality management system, consisting of a set of methods, means and tools, and practical guidelines, additional to those employed to carry out the technical work of the Project, aiming to ensure that the Project work and results are of a uniform high quality. They have been created to ensure 5GMETA meets the stated objectives and complies with the specifications set out in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

The quality WP1 sub-tasks are related to D1.1:

- Coordinate internal Project communication, meetings and workshops.
- Undertake corrective actions, if needed, in order to meet the action plan.
- Identify and manage technical / non-technical risks.
- Pre-check results, taking the initial requirements and objectives into consideration, and make sure that they are internally distributed.
- Ensure that 5GMETA as a whole meets all its defined objectives and delivers high quality results that can generate the expected impact and be exploited by the Project partners.
- Establish procedures for the production of Project results and for their quality assurance.
- Identify the roles and responsibilities for quality management amongst all Project partners.

This Project and Quality Management Plan is applicable to all the activities related to the Project and thus all partners must comply with the processes described herein. However, the terms and provisions of the 5GMETA Grant Agreement (and its annexes) and of the 5GMETA Consortium Agreement will prevail in the event of any inconsistency with the recommendations and guidelines defined in the present document.

1.3 Intended audience

The intended audience of this deliverable are first the 5GMETA consortium partners, as it describes all processes related to the monitoring and reporting of their work in the project and to the Grant Agreement with EC. It is also intended for the EC services, since this document describes 5GMETA project management and quality monitoring processes.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable and its relation with other work packages/deliverables

This deliverable firstly addresses the 5GMETA Project structure (Section 2), including the consortium partners, Work Package structure, organisational structure, and decision-making. Then, in Section 3, the management procedures are described, including project internal procedures, management and communication tools, reporting, deliverable and document management, risk management and additional support processes.

This deliverable does not address innovation management and data management procedures, which are addressed in dedicated deliverables:

- D1.2: Innovation management plan.
- D1.3: Data management plan.

1.5 Main changes from previous version

The main changes of the present version of the deliverable compared with the previously delivered version are:

- The structure of the deliverable has been reorganised to explain more clearly the management tools and procedures.
- Added detailed information about 5GMETA's management and communication tools (Section 3).
- Added tables with the names of the members of 5GMETA's PMT (Table 3), SC (Table 4) and WP leaders (Table 5).
- Added impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on Project Management (Section 4.1.1).
- Added more information to Section 4.1 about 5GMETA's Steering Committee, General Tracking, and Work Package meetings.
- Added new section to describe 5GMETA's gender balance in decision-making (Section 4.1.7).
- Added new section to describe 5GMETA's approach to address Review Report recommendations (Section 4.1.8).
- Added guidelines to write deliverables to include only meaningful information and to avoid repetitions among deliverables (Section 4.3.1).
- Added 5GMETA's Risk Register in Annex 1.

2 PROJECT STRUCTURE

2.1 Consortium

The 5GMETA consortium was carefully built and consists of 11 organisations from 4 different countries (see Figure 1), which gather all the necessary background and expertise to achieve the objectives of the project. A balanced combination of research and business will ensure that the value of the outcomes of the project is optimised and that it is of direct relevance to the wider public.

Table 1: List of the partners of the 5GMETA consortium

No.	Partner name	Short	Country
1	FUNDACIÓN CENTRO DE TECNOLOGÍAS DE INTERACCIÓN VISUAL Y COMUNICACIONES VICOMTECH	VICOM	Spain
2	AKKA HIGH TECH	AKKA	France
3	DEKRA TESTING AND CERTIFICATION SAU	DEKRA	Spain
4	EUROPEAN ROAD TRANSPORT TELEMATICS IMPLEMENTATION COORDINATION ORGANISATION – INTELLIGENT TRANSPORT SYSTEMS & SERVICES EUROPE	ERT	Belgium
5	CONSORZIO INTERUNIVERSITARIO PER L'OTTIMIZZAZIONE E LA RICERCA OPERATIVA	ICOOR	Italy
6	INTEMPORA	INT	France
7	LIFTT SPA	LIFTT	Italy
8	FONDAZIONE LINKS – LEADING INNOVATION & KNOWLEDGE FOR SOCIETY	LINKS	Italy
9	NEO GLS	NEO	France
10	INSTITUT VEDECOM	VED	France
11	WIND TRE SPA	WI3	Italy

Figure 1: Geographical distribution of the partners of the 5GMETA consortium

2.2 Work Packages

The tasks of 5GMETA are distributed in line with the expertise of the partners and balanced according to the resources allocated. Partners bring significant background IP, existing working relationships, involvement in funded 5G-PPP projects, and access to SMEs and high-tech start-ups through incubators and to domain experts by means of automotive clusters. The project is organised in 7 Work Packages (WPs), three of which relate to horizontal activities, i.e. project management & coordination (WP1), dissemination & exploitation (WP7) and ethics (WP8), while the others target the different technical Project's objectives. Each WP is led by a partner particularly experienced in the corresponding area, to ensure best practices and work efficiency. The Project structure follows a methodology with 2 iterations and a 3-phased approach for design and implementation, evaluation through innovative demonstrators, and third-party hackathons driven by incubators and clusters.

Table 2: List of 5GMETA Work Packages

WP no.	Work Package title	WP leader
1	PROJECT MANAGEMENT & COORDINATION	1.- VICOM
2	5G FUNCTIONS DESIGN & USE CASES	8.- LINKS
3	5G NETWORK FUNCTIONS AS A DATA PLATFORM	1.- VICOM
4	DATA & DEMONSTRATORS GENERATION	2.- AKKA
5	ACTORS INTEGRATION & SERVICES VALIDATION	5.- ICOOR
6	NEW MARKET ECOSYSTEM	7.- LIFTT
7	DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION	4.- ERT
8	ETHICS REQUIREMENTS	1.-VICOM

Figure 2: Work Package structure and logic

2.3 Organisational structure and decision making

The success of 5GMETA relies to a great extent on the ability of the consortium to implement an efficient management structure and adequate procedures capable of addressing the challenges normally encountered in cooperative projects. This section provides a description of the management framework set up by the consortium to link together all the project components and maintain smooth communication amongst the partners. The structures, roles, responsibilities, and mutual obligations of the partners herein described are duly specified in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement signed before the start of the Project, to which partners must adhere.

2.3.1 Project management structure

A management structure has been defined to ensure control of the project activities (see Figure 3). Partner responsibilities, tasks and expected results have been defined before the start of 5GMETA, in order to avoid grey areas and misunderstandings. The proposed project management structure and procedures are designed to provide leadership to enable the project to achieve its objectives, goals and to represent a framework for making structural decisions. It will provide for effective cooperation between the various stakeholders and will offer opportunities for supporting innovative initiatives. It will include measures for continuous consultation with external stakeholders to discuss and confirm vision, directions and agree on priorities. Provisions will also be made for the management of knowledge, protection of intellectual property rights and other innovation-related activities arising in the project.

Figure 3: Diagram of the Project management structure

2.3.2 Project coordination and Project Management Team

VICOM is the Project Coordinator (PC) with the responsibility for the overall coordination of the project, including all the administrative, contractual and financial management of the project. As such, VICOM is the direct interface between the project consortium and the European Commission. Coordination activities which will be carried by VICOM for the entire duration of the project are the following:

- Convene the Grant Agreement;
- Definition and application of management procedures;
- Organize the meetings of the various management bodies, preparation and distribution of their agenda and minutes;
- Prepare and follow-up all project meetings (notification, agenda, chairing and reporting);
- Chair the Steering Committee (SC);
- Coordinate all technical activities and detect deviations;
- Monitor project progress, workload consumption and tracking cost related to the budget;
- Checking and approving the documents generated in the project, ensuring a quality process.
- Keep partners informed about project progress;
- Manage reporting to the Commission and serve as the administrative liaison to the EC and as Project secretary and archive.

VICOM as the leading party within the 5GMETA Project will spread the idea of excellence throughout the project and will guide the partners by issuing appropriate rules for team working and assuring quality. Within the Project Management Team (PMT), six roles have been defined:

- The **Project Coordinator (PC)** is the ultimate reference for the overall responsibility for the organisation, planning and control monitoring of the quality of the technical achievements. This is the person who acts as the interface with the EC and with any third party. The 5GMETA Project Coordinator is Dr. Oihana Otaegui (VICOM).
- The **Technical Manager (TM)** assists the Project Manager in organisation, planning, and control of the project, as well as monitoring technical achievements. The TM coordinates interactions between WPs and is responsible for the supervision of the overall progress of the Project. The 5GMETA Technical Manager is Dr. Gorka Vélez (VICOM).

- The **Administrative Manager (AM)** assists, supports and advises on topics related to legal, financial and contractual aspects of the Project. The Administrative Manager will be Ms. Dorleta García (VICOM).
- The **Innovation Manager (IM)** coordinates the work of all 5GMETA partners to ensure that the Project results can be optimally exploited and commercialised. The IM provides best practices on innovation management and reports to the SC. The Innovation Manager is Ms. Esther Novo (VICOM).
- The **Data Manager (DM)** leads the data management plan tasks and ensures data collection, storage and handling, as well as their publication as part of the EC Open Research Data Pilot. The DM raises potential issues and proposes solutions for dealing with data privacy and data protection regulations. The Data Manager is Mr. Benoit Baurens (AKKA).

The **Quality Manager (QM)** leads the quality management plan tasks ensuring a high quality of Deliverables, the achievement of Milestones and the overall Project outcomes. In particular, the QM leads and performs the following quality management tasks:

- Operate and maintain the 5GMETA quality management system;
- Assure that all Deliverables reports conform to the criteria defined in the 5GMETA Deliverable review process, and that, in its support role to the PC, Deliverables comply with the specifications given in the 5GMETA Grant Agreement;
- Verify that all Project Deliverables reports are of high quality and comply with contractual requirements as set by the EC in the Grant Agreement;
- Suggest action to prevent the occurrence of any non-conformity;
- Identify and record any relevant problem;
- Recommend and/or provide solutions to be approved by the PMT and/or SC;
- Verify the implementation of solutions;
- Monitor and control further processing, delivery or implementation of any preferred solution to ensure that any reported non-conformance has been corrected.

Hence, the QM supports the PC in identifying problems related to quality during internal reviews and/or audits. When problems are identified, the PC and PMT are responsible for discussing and initiating measures and, with the support of the QM, follow the process through until a resolution is reached. All problems are raised within the PMT and/or SC meetings chaired by the PC, and the minutes should record the agreed actions and timing.

The Quality Manager is Julie Castermans (ERT).

Table 3: Members of 5GMETA PMT.

Role	Name	Organisation
Project Manager (PM)	Oihana Otaegui	VICOM
Technical Manager (TM)	Gorka Vélez	VICOM
Administrative Manager (AM)	Dorleta García	VICOM
Innovation Manager (IM)	Esther Novo	VICOM
Data Manager (DM)	Benoit Baurens	AKKA
Quality Manager (QM)	Julie Castermans	ERT

2.3.3 Steering Committee

The 5GMETA Steering Committee (SC) is comprised of a representative of each partner taking part in the project and is chaired by the PC. The list of the SC members was agreed at the project's kick-off meeting and has been updated periodically on each SC meeting. The aim of the SC is to advise and support the PC's decisions on operational and management matters. Where appropriate, the SC will try to resolve conflicts as they arise, otherwise it will refer the matter to the PC with the necessary recommendations. The SC is responsible for all decisions of general nature made in the frame of the 5GMETA Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement, including:

- Any expenditure (except those already agreed upon in the budget);
- Any major change in the nature of the Project;
- The preparation of the budget and any proposed amendments;
- Any transaction between the consortium and a third party;
- Ownership and access rights of the results.

The decisions within the SC are taken preferably by consensus. In case of disagreements, the decision will be put to a unanimous vote of all representatives, where a simple majority is sufficient.

As an update from the previous Project Management Plan, now each organisation defines a deputy member to the SC, in addition to the main contact. The role of the deputy is to represent its organisation in the SC meetings that the main contact cannot attend. The deputy member receives the same communications than the main contact.

Table 4: 5GMETA SC members

Organisation	Main contact	Deputy
VICOM	Oihana Otaegui	Gorka Vélez
AKKA	Benoit Baurens	Fatma Raissi
DEKRA	Janie Baños	Oscar Castañeda
ERT	Zeljko Jeftic	Peter Schmitting
ICOOR	Mauro Dell'amico	Arslane Hamza-Cherif
INT	Gwenaël Dunand	Benjamin Ballet
LINKS	Daniele Brevi	Edoardo Bonetto
LIFTT	Pierluigi Freni	Guido Panizza
NEO	André Perpey	Mehdi Naciri
VED	Oyunchimeg Shagdar	Pierre Merdrignac
WI3	Gianluca Rizzi	Fabrizio Brasca

2.3.4 Work Package Leaders

The Work Package Leader (WPL) is responsible for the coordination of the work within a WP. In conjunction with the PC and the relevant partners for each WP, the WPL is responsible for the follow up of the work in compliance with the objectives and general scope of work as agreed by the partners. He/she chairs the corresponding WP meetings and is responsible for estimating the resources required for the various tasks within the WP and for drawing up and monitoring suitably detailed plans for executing the work and for producing the Deliverables.

Table 5: 5GMETA WP leaders

WP	WP leader	Organisation
WP1	Oihana Otaegui	VICOM
WP2	Daniele Brevi	LINKS
WP3	Ángel Martín	VICOM
WP4	Djibrilla Amadou Kountche	AKKA
WP5	Arslane Hamza-Cherif	ICOOR
WP6	Pierluigi Freni	LIFTT
WP7	Duygu Özcan	ERT
WP8	Esther Novo	VICOM

3 MANAGEMENT AND COMMUNICATION TOOLS

5GMETA chose Microsoft Teams (MS Teams) as an integral platform for project management and communication. The use of a single tool for most of the daily project management and communication tasks simplifies the complexity of a project of considerable size, with multiple sub-teams of experts and trial sites working in parallel and collaborating.

3.1 Task planning and tracking

MS Teams is used to keep track of the progress achieved in each task. This tool enables WP and Task Leaders to align, delegate and keep track of the work among the various partners. Additionally, the dependencies among the various activities of the different use cases and trial sites have to be clear, completion of certain tasks (affecting others) has to be tracked, and their progress has to be monitored. This guarantees that 5GMETA will deliver its outputs on time and aligned with the Description of Action of the Grant Agreement.

Each task is defined with a start and due date, dependency with other tasks (if they exist), explanation of the implementation details of the task and they are assigned to a specific person within a 5GMETA partner, who is responsible for making sure the task is completed on time and monitoring and updating its progress. The various inter-connected tasks provide an end-to-end picture of all the activities that need to be performed within the project.

MS Teams provides a Kanban-style board for each channel of a workspace. In the 5GMETA workspace, there is a channel per WP. Therefore, each WP has its own board managed by the WP leader.

Figure 4: WP3 Task board in MS Teams.

Figure 5: Sample task of WP3 in MS Teams.

MS Teams also provides the possibility of visualising the statistics of the task board.

Figure 6 Statistics of WP4 board in MS Teams.

3.2 Document editing and repository

Every Teams channel has a SharePoint team site. SharePoint is the tool chosen in 5GMETA for storing files in the cloud and making them accessible to the whole consortium. Sharepoint is fully integrated in Teams, so each WP channel can access to its file repository directly from Teams.

Figure 7: WP3 file repository.

SharePoint allows for storage, retrieval, searching, archiving, tracking, management, and reporting on electronic documents and records. SharePoint's integration with Microsoft Office 365 allows for collaborative real-time editing which is a feature extensively used in 5GMETA in many working documents and deliverable drafts.

Figure 8: Online edition of D1.1 in MS Teams.

3.3 Wiki for management procedures

Teams also includes the possibility of adding a Wiki per channel. In 5GMETA, a Wiki has been added to WP1 channel to describe the management procedures. This way the procedures are easy to find and navigate, facilitating their implementation.

3.4 Scheduling conference calls

The conference calls of 5GMETA are scheduled and conducted using MS Teams. The use of a single tool for all conference calls minimises the typical problems with conference calls such as audio or screen sharing problems.

Figure 9: Starting a WP2 conference call in Teams.

3.5 Chat

The use of chats is promoted in 5GMETA as a way of fostering project's internal communication beyond scheduled meetings. Teams includes chat functionality and chats can be started with any person or group of people registered in the 5GMETA workspace.

3.6 Mail groups

To ensure that the Consortium receives relevant information in a timely manner without an excessive use of email, Project communication reflects the structure of the Project and targets the smallest possible group of members via email. Targeted information sharing is based on the classification of internal communication as communication related to project activity execution.

The following mail groups has been created by VICOM:

- A mail group including all the consortium partners (technical, financial and contractual contact points): 5GMETA@vicomtech.org;

- Dedicated mail group for each WP:
 - 5GMETA_wp1@vicomtech.org
 - 5GMETA_wp2@vicomtech.org
 - 5GMETA_wp3@vicomtech.org
 - 5GMETA_wp4@vicomtech.org
 - 5GMETA_wp5@vicomtech.org
 - 5GMETA_wp6@vicomtech.org
 - 5GMETA_wp7@vicomtech.org
- Dedicated mail group for WP leaders: 5gmeta-wp-leaders@vicomtech.org
- Dedicated mail group for SC: 5gmeta-sc@vicomtech.org

VICOM is responsible for maintaining the above mail groups and creating new ones if needed. All partners shall promptly communicate via e-mail any change/update of contact details and/or personnel involved to VICOM, who will modify accordingly the distribution lists and the access rights to MS Teams in order to ensure that information are not misused or missed. VICOM shall implement any change within one week from the communication and inform other partners as relevant, using the updated distribution lists or via Microsoft Teams.

4 MANAGEMENT PROCEDURES

4.1 Project Internal Procedures

In order to ensure a rapid and efficient execution of the project tasks, dedicated management tools and procedures, fitting all specific management requirements has been proposed from the start. These tools are placed under the responsibility of the Steering Committee and Work Package Leaders. To ensure the project maintains rhythms and a team dynamic, the following meeting types and intervals are being used:

- Steering Committee meetings: one-hour conference calls every month. The PMT will also attend the calls.
- Project progress tracking meeting: one-hour conference calls every two weeks;
- Work Package meetings: one-hour conference calls every two weeks for those WPs and tasks in focus and for partners active in the tasks;
- General Assembly meetings: plenary and/or technical meetings will be hold in-person every six months and hosted by a partner (due to COVID-19 pandemic situation, at the time of writing this deliverable report, these are replaced by web-conference calls)
- Internal reporting: 360-degree reviews of Project every six months (or as necessary).

All the above meetings and conference calls will be used to track technical, financial and management tasks against plans, identify and assess issues and risks, assess forthcoming deadlines and Milestones. The agreed team meetings setting along with fluent email, chat and conference call communications has proven satisfactory and it is intended to be maintained until the end of the project. Ad-hoc meetings will also be scheduled as needed to tackle specific topics.

4.1.1 Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on Project Management

The COVID-19 pandemic has been identified as a risk and is registered on the EU portal under Unforeseen Risk number U1. The risk can be found in Annex 1 as 5GMETA.Risk10.

The main effect of the pandemic on Project Management has been the lack of face-to face meetings. The PMT has been continuously monitoring the timelines and plans to ensure the effects on the Project's results are limited to non-existing. To achieve this, the main mitigating measures that have been implemented are monitoring for early detection of deviations and the requirement of having alternative plans when travel, close cooperation or on-site effort are needed.

At the time of writing this deliverable, there were no measurements in place in the European Union to prevent the 5GMETA consortium members to travel or to gather, so the face-to-face meetings will be restarted soon. In any case, this risk will be monitored, and risk mitigation actions will be updated during the whole duration of the project.

4.1.2 Steering Committee meetings

The main objectives of the monthly SC meetings are:

- to address high-level decisions;
- to monitor the risks defined in the Risk Register and identify new risks (see Section 5: Risk Management);
- to monitor the correct implementation of the management procedures.

To address the last objective, the Technical Manager, the Innovation Manager, the Data Manager and the Quality Manager are also invited to the meetings in addition to the SC members.

The first point of the agenda is always the confirmation of SC members, where any update in the SC is reported. After each meeting, an updated version of the SC members and the Risk Register is frozen, versioned and archived in pdf format.

The overlap with the General Tracking Meetings is minimised as much as possible to avoid repetitions. The slides presented during the meeting as well as the minutes are available to everybody in the MS Teams repository to ensure transparency in decision making.

The schedule of the SC meetings is the following:

Table 6: Schedule of SC meetings

Frequency	Day	Time	Host
Monthly	First Friday of every month	9:00-10:00	VICOM

4.1.3 General Tracking Meetings

The bi-weekly General Tracking Meetings are open to everybody in the consortium and their main objectives are:

- to monitor the progress of each active WP and deliverable;
- to identify issues that might be blocking a WP, to anticipate deviations and propose solutions or mitigation actions;
- to present the short-term next steps of each WP;
- to coordinate actions between WPs;
- to give an overall picture of the project progress to the consortium.

Each WP leader presents the slides corresponding to their WP, following the same template.

Figure 10: Template of first slide to be presented by each WP in General Tracking Meetings

Status of deliverable Dx.y

• **Quick overview of deliverable:**

Ref	Task(s)	Deliverable title	Due date	Lead partner	Editor name	Partners involved
Dx.y			2021/xx/yy			

• **Checklist of deliverable status:**

Step	Done?
Table of Contents defined	X
Internal reviewers assigned	X
Contents written	
Internal peer review	
Quality check	
Deliverable submission	

• **Actions leading up to deliverable deadline:**

- ...
- ...

5

Figure 11: Template of second slide to be presented by each WP in General Tracking Meetings

The slide depicted in Figure 11 is duplicated per active deliverable. If there are no active deliverables in the WP, this slide is removed.

Monitoring risks/issues

What is or will be blocking your WP? What do or what will you need?

Noted or foreseeable issue	Proposed solution

6

Figure 12: Template of third slide to be presented by each WP in General Tracking Meetings

Wrap-up: short-term next steps

Action	Deadline	Who

7
14/10/2021

Figure 13: Template of fourth slide to be presented by each WP in General Tracking Meetings

The schedule of the General Tracking meetings is the following:

Table 7: Schedule of General Tracking meetings

Frequency	Day	Time	Host
Bi-weekly	Friday	10:00-11:00	VICOM

4.1.4 Work Package and task Meetings

The WP meetings are scheduled by the WP leaders for those active WPs. In addition, when necessary, dedicated calls are also arranged on demand. The main objectives of the WP meetings are:

- clarify the scope of the tasks and the role of each partner;
- assign responsibilities;
- track the progress in more detail than in the General Tracking Meetings;
- identify potential deviations from the work plan;
- discuss next steps.

4.1.5 Conflict resolution

The Consortium Agreement has been negotiated and agreed among the 5GMETA consortium partners in order to define their obligations and rights under the project. The Steering Committee is in charge of the resolution of the conflicts that may arise during the execution of the project. Those decisions may be classified as follows: on-going management of project, review or amendment of the work plan defined in the Annex I of the Grant Agreement, together with the allocation of the funding provided by the EC, and review or amendment of the terms of the Grant Agreement, the time schedules and budget allocated under the Grant Agreement, and the termination date of the Grant Agreement.

Certain decisions will require approval by the European Commission. If partners do not fulfil their contractual obligations as defined in the Grant Agreement, they will be cautioned by the consortium. All means will be taken to resolve any conflicts that might occur during the Project by unanimous decision of the consortium partners. However, if a unanimous decision cannot be reached within an appropriate time frame, a decision process with a qualified majority vote will be applied via WP leaders. Details of the necessary majority and the competencies to make decisions are specified in the 5GMETA Consortium Agreement.

4.1.6 Self-assessment Audits

The 5GMETA consortium will implement a system of self-assessment audits in the Project. These audits will be based on feedback assessment by project partners, the European Commission and other key project stakeholders not identified at the time of writing of this Deliverable. The purpose of the audits will be team development and appraisal of the Project goals. They shall also facilitate communication and team development within the consortium by providing feedback on partner performance. This technique will underpin a strategy of management by objectives during the project. Furthermore, the process will enable the partners to participate in goal setting and ensure they are aligned with the project goals, provide motivation to the consortium by demonstrating the participative nature of the management process, provide clarity on the definition of project goals and most importantly make the communication and coordination processes of the project more effective and agile. The audits will coincide with project meetings at M6, M12, M18, M24, M30 and M36. The last will take the form of a project closing review. The kick-off meeting has been used to start the process and familiarise the consortium with the process. It also served to allow the consortium reflecting on the proposal preparation and negotiation phases and to ensure that 5GMETA starts with any pertinent issues being addressed from its kick-off.

The audits should be simple avoiding complex processes and foster open and frank discussion on the progress of the project and performance of consortium partners. The expected benefit of this process is to formalise periods of reflection after distinct phases of the project lifecycle, so that inefficiencies and conflicts can be identified, and the appropriate solutions and measures can be adopted. The purpose of this review style is not intended to drive or maximise the project performance, but rather to ensure that expectations of 5GMETA partners and other stakeholders are reasonable and achievable and to ensure the achievement of project goals. Prior to each meeting a brief questionnaire will be circulated to Project principals requesting a self-assessment on the execution of their activities and those of the partners with whom they have worked during the period under consideration. The SC will be asked to provide feedback on the consortium and the project as a whole. The questionnaire will be structured around the goals of the project period under consideration as well as globally, i.e. considering the core values and ambitions of the project purpose. The PC will prepare equivalent assessments. Aside to the project consortium meetings, the SC will hold a review meeting where the assessments will be contrasted and agreed. The output of this process and meetings will be an action plan for the following period addressing objectives to leverage the strengths in the previous period, corrective actions (if necessary), in order to tackle any identified needs of concerned partner(s) to achieve its (their) own goals and contribute appropriately to the overall project objectives.

4.1.7 Gender balance in decision-making

5GMETA's Project Management Team (PMT) is committed to promoting gender equality and it is aligned with European Commission's latest Horizon Europe guidelines. Therefore, it is committed to the integration of the gender dimension into research and innovation content as well as increasing gender balance in decision making. The gender balance of 5GMETA in decision-making at the moment of writing this deliverable is shown in the following table. It can be noted that the majority of the PMT members are women. There are also women in the Steering Committee and among the Work Package Leaders, although they are not majority in these boards.

Table 8: Gender balance in 5GMETA decision making

Decision-making board	Total number of members	Number of women
Project Management Team	6	4
Steering Committee	11	3
Work Package Leaders	8	3

Achieving gender balance in decision-making requires more than just increased representation. In addition to monitoring that an appropriate number of women are on committees, the PMT is continuously examining the decision-making processes to ensure decisions consider gender issues and that women are empowered to take an equal role.

4.1.8 Addressing Review Report recommendations

5GMETA's PC and TM designed and put in place a procedure to address the recommendations and comments included in a EC Review report. First, the Review report is processed by the TM and the PC and the comments that imply recommendations or suggestions are added to a spreadsheet, classified in categories. Then, a responsible is assigned to each comment. Once the responsables are assigned, each of the responsables add a list of actions that consider that need to be taken to address the comment. The complete list of actions is presented to the SC for its approval. If any feedback is received, the spreadsheet is updated accordingly. Once approved, the list of actions becomes a mandate of the SC. This allows to enforce corrective actions to the Project Coordinator (VICOM). The status of the actions is periodically monitored by PC and TM before a General Tracking Meeting (biweekly) or SC meeting (monthly) occurs. If any critical deviation from the action plan is detected, the issue will be addressed

by the SC. If the impact of the deviation is minor, then, the regular General Tracking meetings will be used to address the issue. The flow diagram of the procedure is depicted in Figure 14.

Figure 14 5GMETA procedure to address Review report comments

The spreadsheet template has the following fields per collected recommendation or comment:

- Recommendation/Comment Category
- Recommendation/Comment: exact text extracted from the Review Report
- Action(s) to address recommendation/comment: list of concrete actions
- Responsible: partner in charge of the action. The role is specified when possible (WP leader, etc).
- Status: to select between these options
 - Done.
 - Implemented and monitored.
 - Work in progress.
 - Not implemented.
- Info about implementation status: free text to give more information if necessary.

The colour of the “Status” cells automatically changes depending on the selected option to facilitate the monitoring.

The monitoring spreadsheet of the first Review Report is currently available in Teams (see Figure 15), and a shortcut has been added to the General workspace menu to facilitate finding the file. The

spreadsheet is openly available to the consortium, so all the partners in charge of actions can collaboratively edit the file and update the status of each assigned action.

Recommendation category	Recommendation	Actions to address recommendation	Responsible	Status
Recommendations concerning future work	R11: Make sure you submit all of the deliverables again. The deliverables have to provide more concrete information on the project innovations, and how it is differentiated from current works, architectures, and how this i	Define management procedures, add them to TEAMS Wiki, and enforce them	VICOM	Not implemented
		Schedule periodical steering committee meetings to track implementation of management procedures	VICOM	Done
		Document steering committee meetings (create minutes)	VICOM	Implemented and monitor
		Add summary of activities to next periodical report.	VICOM	Not implemented
R14: Dissemination and exploitation for SGMETA are fundamentally different from other projects. This should be reflected not only in the KPIs but also in the type of actions put into place. All beneficiaries need to contribute to all dissemination activities individually and as a group.	R14: Dissemination and exploitation for SGMETA are fundamentally different from other projects. This should be reflected not only in the KPIs but also in the type of actions put into place. All beneficiaries need to contribute to all dissemination activities individually and as a group.	Add hackaton activities to D7.1	LIFTT	Work in progress
		Add individual dissemination KPIs to D7.1	ERT	Work in progress
		All the partners to give active contribution during the hackathons preparation and execution	LIFTT	Implemented and monitor
		Aprove extension in a Steering Committee meeting.	Steering Committee	Done
R15: The project should consider an extension of at least 6 months (if not more) to recover from the lack of integrated and well-communicated work up to date.	R15: The project should consider an extension of at least 6 months (if not more) to recover from the lack of integrated and well-communicated work up to date.	Adapt Gantt to reflect the extension.	Steering Committee & WP leaders	Done
		Officially apply changes in an Amendment.	VICOM	Work in progress

Figure 15 Review Report spreadsheet available in MS Teams

4.2 Reporting

4.2.1 Periodic and final reports

The Article 20 of the Grant Agreement requires the submission of two Periodic Report respectively covering the periods M01-M18 (Sep. 2020 – Feb. 2022) and M19-M36 (Mar. 2022 – Aug. 2023). The PC (VICOM) must submit such periodic reports within 60 days following the end of each reporting period. This means two periodic reports plus a final report over the duration of the Project. The reports shall be written in English and be compiled and transmitted to the EC by the PC on behalf of the consortium using the periodic reporting functionality in the EC Funding & Tenders Portal. The PC will deal with non-submission of documents in accordance to Article 20.8 of the Grant Agreement. For further information, reference shall be made to the Grant Agreement and H2020 guidelines and templates available at https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/reports_en.htm.

4.2.2 Continuous reporting

In addition to the periodic reports, H2020 provides for a continuous reporting functionality in the Funding & Tenders Portal. This is meant for the beneficiaries to submit deliverables (see Article 19 of the GA), to report on progress in achieving milestones, to follow up of critical risks, ethics issues, publications, communications activities, and the answers to the questionnaire on horizontal issues (see above link for detailed H2020 guidelines or the Grant Agreement).

4.2.3 Deliverables

Deliverables are significant results in the lifecycle of the Project allowing the Project monitoring over time. They indicate how a Work Package (WP) and its associated Tasks and expected output(s)/result(s)

are progressing, whereas they ultimately show that the proposed Project objectives have been achieved. The number of Deliverables per WP depends on their level of complexity. They are meant to provide a track of the developments and outcomes of the Project on a continuous basis and a record of the work done and fulfilment of contractual obligations.

Deliverables are identified in Annex 1 of the GA, which also specifies their timing and conditions. The achievement of each contractual Deliverable (i.e. listed in the Grant Agreement) is formalised through the electronic submission of a deliverable report to the EC by the PC on behalf of the 5GMETA consortium. Indeed, also in case of physical demonstrators, prototypes, tools, etc., a short summary report should be submitted to the EC describing the physical deliverable and stating where it runs and how it can be used. One electronic copy of each deliverable report will have to be provided to the PC by the lead partner. The PC will submit all Deliverables to the EC through the Funding & Tenders Portal.

Every deliverable must meet appropriate quality standards for:

- Achievements and professional quality of work;
- Coverage of the subject, as stated in the contract;
- Being representative of real-life cases (if appropriate);
- Handling of problems or errors (if appropriate);
- Level of detail and amount of supporting information provided to the user;
- Security and confidentiality considerations;
- The approach taken.

4.3 Deliverable management

4.3.1 Guidelines to write deliverables

The following guidelines have been communicated to all project partners and are enforced by the deliverable editors to include only meaningful information and to avoid repetitions among deliverables:

- When drafting the Table of Contents of a deliverable, double check that any of those sections were not covered in a previous deliverable. If this is the case, remove it. There should be no overlap between deliverables.
- Previous deliverables are considered as copyrighted journal papers or books in terms of referencing and avoiding “copy & paste”.
- Copying & pasting text between deliverables is not acceptable, except between the different versions of the same deliverable.
- If a figure from a previous deliverable is essential to explain something, then add it and reference to the original deliverable in the caption. But this should be something exceptional and not the norm.
- If it is necessary to use tables from previous deliverables, then add them in an Annex and reference the original deliverable. But this should be something exceptional and not the norm.

Deliverable reports must follow the following structure:

Table 9: Structure of a Deliverable report

Title	Description
Introductory pages	The report standard includes a cover page, revision and approval status table, table of contents, list of figures, list of tables and glossary.
Glossary	List and description of acronyms/abbreviations used in the report.
Executive summary	This section should be a synopsis, or general overview, summarising the content of the report (1 to 2 pages).
Introduction	This optional section may contain information about the data sources, context of the production of the report, special explanations of importance for the reading or the use of the information contained in the report, etc.
Full description of the approach and results	This is the main part of the report and should explain clearly how the results were achieved, including diagrams or pictures to illustrate technical/scientific points. For prototypes, test results, etc., it should contain a user manual, photos and description of location, specifications, test scenario or any other appropriate information.
Conclusions	This optional section should be a summary of the major Deliverable achievements (maximum ½ page).
References	This optional section should list documents, publications and other key references / bibliography mentioned in the report.
Annexes	Annexes may be necessary to present additional information. If needed, annexes may remain confidential and not be made public, but only submitted to the EC.

4.3.2 Deliverable life cycle

4.3.2.1 Internal validation

For each deliverable, one partner is identified as deliverable leader (taken from Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement, or the updated Annex 1 in case of contract amendment). The leading partner appoints a responsible person for the deliverable, the deliverable editor, who is responsible for the production and quality of the related report in terms of both content and form. However, before submission to EC, the deliverable report will be peer reviewed sufficiently in advance to allow for proof reading, feedback and updates.

The deliverable lead editor shall:

- define the report structure in line with the general structure given;
- collect inputs from contributors/authors, check their quality and integrate them into a draft report;
- circulate such draft report for revision until agreement is reached from all partners involved;
- produce the final version of the Deliverable report and send it for the peer review;
- revise the report taking into account the peer review and produce the final version of the Deliverable report for the final quality check by the QM and PC for submission to the EC.

4.3.2.2 Review process

For each deliverable, the review process shall be carried out as follows:

- Two reviewers per deliverable are the standard. However, one reviewer might be used for minor / simpler deliverables, at the request of the relevant WP Leader;
- The reviewers are from the Project Consortium, but not directly involved in the work related to the deliverable;
- No template for the peer review will be provided. Track changes versions are preferable and will be kept as record of the peer review.

4.3.2.3 Submission to the EC

Once peer reviewed and quality checked, the PC will submit the deliverable report to the EC through the continuous reporting functionality in the Funding & Tenders Portal. The PC also notifies the Project Consortium of the Deliverable submission and its availability in a specific folder of Microsoft Teams (the 5GMETA collaborative web platform).

Draft versions of each deliverable report shall be produced in **MS Word format**, while the final version to be submitted must be produced in **PDF format**.

4.3.2.4 Timeline

The following timeline must be followed with each deliverable life cycle:

Table 10: Preparation and submission steps for the periodic / final reports and Project Deliverables

Step	Action	Responsible	Delivery to	Latest deadline
1	Write report	Deliverable editor	Peer reviewers	3 weeks before submission deadline
2	Internal peer review	Peer reviewers	Deliverable editor	2 weeks before submission deadline
2	Deliverable revision	Deliverable editor	Quality Manager	1 week before submission deadline

4	Final Quality Check	QM	Deliverable editor	4 days before submission deadline
5	Final deliverable revision	Deliverable editor	PC	1 working day before submission deadline
6	Report submission	PC	EC	Submission deadline

4.3.2.5 Deliverable status

Each deliverable will, at any given moment, have a status described by one of the following statements:

Table 11 Report and deliverable status

Status	Description
Open	Not started
Ongoing	Started with defined structure and, possibly draft version available, but not completed
Done	Completed, but not yet peer reviewed or not approved by Quality Manager or PC.
Submitted	Reviewed and approved at all Project levels, submitted to the EC, available for use Microsoft Teams platform, and (if dissemination level is public) published on the Project website
Delayed	Initial deadline will not be met
Cancelled	Deliverable has been cancelled and will not be achieved

4.3.3 List of Deliverables

The following Deliverables are listed in Annex I of the 5GMETA Grant Agreement. Each Deliverable has a reference number and title, and its realisation process is under the responsibility of the corresponding Deliverable Leader as well as the WPL and Task Leader. During the Project execution, the responsible leader, contributors and reviewers will be identified for each Deliverable and their names communicated to the Project partners well in advance for proper execution of production and delivery processes.

Table 12 List of 5GMETA deliverables

Del. #	Del. Title	WP #	Leader	Peer Review	Type	Diss. level	Due date
D1.1	Project and quality management plan	WP1.1	VICOM	DEKRA VICOM	Report	CO	3
D1.2	Innovation management plan	WP1.1	VICOM	ERT LINKS	Report	CO	6
D1.3	Data management plan	WP1.2	AKKA	VICOM INT	ORDP	CO	6
D1.4	Innovation management report	WP1.1	VICOM	ICOOR DEKRA	Report	CO	36
D2.1	5G requirements & standards	WP2.8	LINKS	WI3 VICOM	Report	PU	5

D2.2	5GMETA use cases and their requirements	WP2.10	VED	AKKA ICOOR	Report	PU	6
D2.3	Initial definition of the 5GMETA architecture	WP2.2	AKKA	VED NEO	Report	PU	8
D2.4	Initial definition of validation metrics	WP2.10	VED	DEKRA INT	Report	PU	12
D2.5	Final definition of the 5GMETA architecture	WP2.2	AKKA	VED NEO	Report	PU	24
D2.6	Final definition of validation metrics	WP2.10	VED	DEKRA INT	Report	PU	24
D3.1	Initial 5G architecture and interfaces	WP3.2	AKKA	NEO LINKS	Report	CO	5
D3.2	First release of 5GMETA data functions	WP3.1	VICOM	AKKA ICOOR	Report	CO	18
D3.3	Final 5G architecture and interfaces	WP3.2	AKKA	NEO LINKS	Report	CO	20
D3.4	Final release of 5GMETA data functions	WP3.1	VICOM	AKKA ICOOR	Report	CO	30
D4.1	Initial 5GMETA implementation & integration	WP4.2	AKKA	VED VICOM	Report	PU	16
D4.2	Initial Infrastructure preparation and datasets compilation	WP4.9	NEO	AKKA VICOM	Report	PU	16
D4.3	Initial innovative services	WP4.2	AKKA	INT VICOM	Report	PU	18
D4.4	Final 5GMETA implementation & integration	WP4.2	AKKA	VED VICOM	Report	PU	28
D4.5	Final Infrastructure preparation and datasets compilation	WP4.10	VED	AKKA VICOM	Report	PU	28
D4.6	Final innovative services	WP4.2	AKKA	INT VICOM	Report	PU	30
D5.1	Integration methodology of 5GMETA for third parties	WP5.10	VED	INT LINKS	Report	PU	12
D5.2	Common evaluation framework	WP5.5	ICOOR	AKKA VED	Report	PU	14
D5.3	Initial 5GMETA innovative services and platform validation	WP5.3	DEKRA	VICOM NEO	Report	PU	21
D5.4	Monitoring and operation dashboard	WP5.2	AKKA	WI3 DEKRA	Report	PU	30
D5.5	Final 5GMETA innovative services and platform validation	WP5.3	DEKRA	VICOM LIFFT	Report	PU	34

D6.1	Market research and stakeholder mapping	WP6.8	LINKS	LIFTT VICOM	Report	PU	8
D6.2	New business models	WP6.8	LINKS	LIFTT VICOM	Report	PU	10
D6.3	Strategy for engaging new actors	WP6.7	LIFTT	ERT ICOOR	Report	PU	12
D6.4	Initial activities with business incubators	WP6.7	LIFTT	ERT VICOM	Report	PU	24
D6.5	Final report on activities with business incubators	WP6.7	LIFTT	ERT VICOM	Report	PU	34
D6.6	Market outreach plan	WP6.7	LIFTT	VICOM WI3	Report	PU	35
D6.7	Recommendations for fostering a new CAM market ecosystem beyond 5GMETA	WP6.5	ICOOR	VICOM ERT	Report	PU	35
D7.1	Dissemination & communication strategy	WP7.4	ERT	VICOM LIFTT	Report	PU	3
D7.2	5GMETA Website and other communication materials	WP7.4	ERT	VICOM LIFTT	Report	PU	3
D7.3	First report on dissemination activities	WP7.4	ERT	VICOM LIFTT	Report	PU	18
D7.4	5GMETA platform commercialisation strategy	WP7.5	ICOOR	DEKRA ERT	Report	PU	18
D7.5	Report on the implementation of the 5GMETA platform commercialisation strategy	WP7.5	ICOOR	DEKRA ERT	Report	PU	36
D7.6	Final report on dissemination activities	WP7.4	ERT	VICOM INT	Report	PU	36
D7.7	Recommendations to Authorities and Standardisation bodies	WP7.4	ERT	NEO WI3	Report	PU	36
D8.1	H - Requirement No. 1	WP8.1	VICOM	Ethics expert (VICOM)	Ethics	CO	6
D8.2	H - Requirement No. 2	WP8.1	VICOM	Ethics expert (VICOM)	Ethics	CO	6
D8.3	H - Requirement No. 3	WP8.1	VICOM	Ethics expert (VICOM)	Ethics	CO	6

D8.4	POPD - Requirement No. 4	WP8.1	VICOM	Ethics expert (VICOM)	Ethics	CO	6
D8.5	POPD - Requirement No. 5	WP8.1	VICOM	Ethics expert (VICOM)	Ethics	CO	6
D8.6	POPD - Requirement No. 6	WP8.1	VICOM	Ethics expert (VICOM)	Ethics	CO	6
D8.7	POPD - Requirement No. 7	WP8.1	VICOM	Ethics expert (VICOM)	Ethics	CO	6
D8.8	POPD - Requirement No. 8	WP8.1	VICOM	Ethics expert (VICOM)	Ethics	CO	6
D8.9	POPD - Requirement No. 9	WP8.1	VICOM	Ethics expert (VICOM)	Ethics	CO	6
D8.10	POPD - Requirement No. 10	WP8.1	VICOM	Ethics expert (VICOM)	Ethics	CO	6
D8.11	POPD - Requirement No. 11	WP8.1	VICOM	Ethics expert (VICOM)	Ethics	CO	6
D8.12	POPD - Requirement No. 12	WP8.1	VICOM	Ethics expert (VICOM)	Ethics	CO	6
D8.13	POPD - Requirement No. 13	WP8.1	VICOM	Ethics expert (VICOM)	Ethics	CO	6
D8.14	POPD - Requirement No. 14	WP8.1	VICOM	Ethics expert (VICOM)	Ethics	CO	6
D8.15	POPD - Requirement No. 15	WP8.1	VICOM	Ethics expert (VICOM)	Ethics	CO	6
D8.16	GEN - Requirement No. 16	WP8.1	VICOM	Ethics expert (VICOM)	Ethics	CO	6

4.4 Document management

This section describes the processes to be used for document management and for related exchanges between Project partners with the aim of assuring confidentiality, security, traceability, and consistency of information exchanged. Aspects related to knowledge management, handling of IPR, access rights

and confidential information are not dealt within this document. Detailed information is included in the 5GMETA Consortium Agreement.

4.4.1 Document referencing

All partners shall ensure that the document referencing is detailed and consistent. The following nomenclature must be used for all documents issued within the 5GMETA Project. The coding for all files and documents is defined as **5GMETA_Xxxx_Vx.y**, followed by the file extension (i.e.: .doc, .ppt, .xls, etc.), where:

- **Xxxx** is a short title easing document identification (e.g., D1.1_Project-quality-mgt-plan).
- **Vx.y** is the version number and sub-number (e.g. 1.0, 1.1, 3.0); official versions (i.e. documents actually released by the 5GMETA consortium) shall have a version number x.0, while internal/draft versions shall be referenced x.y, with y starting from 0.

4.4.2 Document Templates

All 5GMETA documentation shall use one of the templates developed for the project, which are stored on the collaborative web platform Microsoft Teams, under the WP7 folder.

4.4.3 Confidentiality and Dissemination Level

For each deliverable and report, the confidentiality / dissemination levels as well as the property / copyright must be clearly indicated in the document itself. The dissemination level (public or confidential), is specified for each Project Deliverable in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement. All other documents and reports created within 5GMETA are by default considered 5GMETA confidential. The corresponding legal mentions are included in each document template and should not be removed, unless a more restricted copyright applies (e.g., at WP / Task level, organisation level, etc.). The following codes must be used to specify the dissemination level:

- PU = Public;
 - CO = Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the EC services);
 - INT = Internal, only for members of the Consortium (excluding the EC services).
- Note: the level INT typically applies to internal working documents of the project consortium (e.g., meeting minutes, etc.) and can NOT be used for contractual reports submitted to the EC (such as deliverables, periodic reports).

If needed, it is possible to create a **public version** of (part of) a confidential document, under the condition that the owners of the confidential document agree, unanimously and in writing, to release such public version. In this case, a new document code should be given in order to distinguish between versions having different confidentiality / dissemination level.

4.5 Risk Management

4.5.1 Objective

The implementation of a risk management procedure aims at providing a structured approach to the project monitoring through the identification of risks and proper consideration of mitigation strategies, the improvement of the plans, schedules and budgets, and (where needed) the implementation of recovery actions for the achievement of the project objectives.

The Risk Register established in 5GMETA is reviewed and updated in each SC meeting. After each SC meeting, the revised Risk Register is versioned, and a copy archived in pdf format.

4.5.2 Risk Management Procedure

The risk management procedure is an iterative process that is used throughout the life cycle of the 5GMETA project and consists in the following phases:

1. **Identification & management:** The identification and management of all Project related risks falls under the responsibility of a WPL / PMT member, appointed as Risk Owner. The owner of a risk is identified based on the specific perimeter of action. The PC is by default the owner of any other risk falling outside the perimeter of a specific WP.
2. **Assessment:** All risks shall be analysed and allocated to a category of probability ('High', 'Medium' or 'Low'). Each category will have a different level of impact on the Project, as defined below:
 - *High* – will add significant issues to the Project (timeline, budget, achievement of results); represents a major problem for which there is currently no solution; the risk requires decision by all PMT & SC members;
 - *Medium* – will add minor issues to the Project; the risk has the potential of being resolved at a working or PMT level, as considered appropriate;
 - *Low* – minimal impact on the Project but could be a threat; if the risk arises, it can be dealt with easily, at working level.
3. **Plan & implementation:** Action plans for each risk are defined and approved by the Risk Owner or, depending on the impact of the risk, by all PMT & SC members. An action plan may encompass several actions. Should the Risk Owner consider that he/she is not in a position to implement the mitigation action(s) by him/her-self, the PC / PMT / SC may nominate one or more Action(s) Owner(s) at WP / Task level. The Action Owner is fully accountable to implement risk management actions and to report to the Risk Owner for the update of the risk management plan, which can be:
 - preventive actions to remove the cause of the risk;
 - mitigation actions to reduce the probability and/or the impact of the risk;
 - recovery actions to reduce the impact after the risk has happened (i.e., it has become an issue).
4. **Monitoring:** This risk management includes the following processes:
 - following up risks' mitigation actions;
 - monitoring risks by detecting new risks or modification of current known risks;
 - re-assessing risks according to implementation results of mitigation actions / Project evolution;
 - preparing risks reports to higher management (PC / PMT / SC).

4.5.3 Risk register

Risks are managed with the help of a risks register which identifies the risk identification and the mitigation plan, and allows monitoring the progress of each of the identified risks. As it contains non-confidential information, it will be shared with all partners. Such register has been created as an MS Excel spreadsheet which contains the following columns (see Annex 1):

Table 13: Structure of the Risk Register

Column title	Description
Risk ID	Reference number of the risk – maintained by the tool.
WP / Task	Makes reference to the WP / Task number which is related to the risk. When several WPs or Tasks from different WPs are affected by a risk, the word "Project" is used.

Risk Description	Accurate description of risk.
Impact	Description of impact of the risk on the Project (objectives, schedule, costs).
Impact level	High, Medium, Low.
Control / Mitigation	Description of how the risk is monitored and managed.
Risk Owner	Name and e-mail address of the person who takes charge of the risk.
Initiation date	Date or period when the risk has been identified.
Trigger date	Date or period of the Project life when the risk is likely to occur.
Probability	The level of the risk ('High', 'Medium', or 'Low') at various moments in time ('original' when the risk is identified, 'current' at the moment of review, 'target' once the risk is under control).
Action ID	ID of relevant action(s) identified in the mitigation / contingency plan.
Action description	Description of relevant action(s) identified in the mitigation / contingency plan.
Action owner	Name and e-mail address of the person who takes charge of the mitigation / contingency action.
Due date	Deadline for performing and reporting on the mitigation / contingency action.
Additional comments	Any additional information about the risk and relevant mitigation / contingency actions.

The project Risk Register is stored on Microsoft Teams under “WP1” channel and has been populated with the Risks outlined in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement and some new previously unforeseen risks. WP Leaders should provide the PC and PMT with relevant information to update this register as often as needed, by filling in or updating the Risk Register spreadsheet with risks and actions scheduled (risk descriptions, risk probability, actions descriptions). The Risk Register is reviewed on each SC meeting and once approved, the changes are uploaded to the EC portal.

WP1 - PROJECT MANAGEMENT ... Posts Files Wiki Risk Register

File Home Insert Draw Page Layout Formulas Data Review View Help Open in Desktop App Tell me what you want to do Editing Copy Link

fx According to the specification defined in WP2, and integrating the platform created through WP3 will be able to implement different use cases and business logics within the demonstrators developed in WP4 validated in WP5.

Risk ID	WP	Risk Description (The risk is that if...)	Impact (Then...)	Impact level	Control / Mitigation (How the risk is monitored & managed)	Risk Owner role (organization)	Initiation Date When it is identified	Trigger Date When it will occur	Probability original	Probability current	Probability target
5GMETA Risk06	4, 5	The 5GMETA demonstrators do not implement the new business logics adequately and do not satisfy needs from new automotive players or new markets.	The potential of 5GMETA platform is not sufficiently demonstrated.	Medium	According to the specification defined in WP2, and integrating the platform created through WP3 will be able to implement different use cases and business logics within the demonstrators developed in WP4 validated in WP5. The selection of representative use cases for a variety of customer segments and with different added value models will cover all business corners that will be validated by demonstrators. A wider applicability will be backed by the hackathons driven by incubators and clusters from the feedback captured from participant SMEs and start-ups.	WP4L (AKKA)	1-Sep-2020		Low	Low	Low
5GMETA Risk07	5	Underestimation of the costs required for the deployment of demonstrators.	Increase of the project expenses.	Low	Consortium will estimate the infrastructure required for a set of use cases, representative for different customer segments and added value models. WINDTRE brings a 5G infrastructure to deploy Edge Network Functions of 5GMETA platform operating data pipelines, monitored and controlled by a central 5GMETA server for accountability and configuration. Servers providing services and apps will be provided by use case/demonstrator leaders invoking 5GMETA APIs.	WP5 Leader (ICOOR)	1-Sep-2020		Low	Low	Low
5GMETA Risk08	6, 7	Dissemination, standardisation and exploitation of the product not successful.	Project does not reach dissemination, standardisation or market targets.	High	WP6 will actively focus on the identification of market audience and business models. The consortium includes organisations, well-positioned in the 5G and automotive fields with influence in standardisation bodies and in the sector.	WP7 Leader (ERT)	1-Sep-2020		Low	Low	Low
		Conflicts of interest between partners.	No agreement on commercial		All partners involved in 5GMETA are complementary; bringing in the project a specific expertise that none of the others	T7 A1 leader					

Foreseen Risks (Annex 1 GA) Unforeseen Risks Risk Records

Calculation Mode: Automatic Workbook Statistics Give Feedback to Microsoft 100%

Figure 16: 5GMETA Risk Register stored in MS Teams.

4.6 Support processes

4.6.1 Deviation and Recovery Plan

Deviations from plan could result from strategic factors and/or dynamic factors.

- **Strategic factors:**

- changes in the context of the Project: new regulations (making the work in a particular activity either impossible to perform due to strict regulations or irrelevant), new situation of the market (resulting in products goals being superseded), or new state-of-the-art (resulting in a scientific achievement becoming obsolete);
- changes in the strategy of partners due to internal constraints such as important restructuring, or due to external constraints such as being purchased by another company, default of payment, bankruptcy, etc.;
- changes in the strategy of the EC resulting in cuts in the planned funding, major delay of the European and/or National advanced funds or cost reimbursements.

- **Dynamic factors:**

- major internal contingencies (logistic, human, financial problems, etc.) met by partners;
- major conflicts between partners;
- major disagreement with the EC;
- lack of skills of partners;

- deficiencies in the different levels of governance of the Project.

The consequences of the problems explained above could be:

- impossibility to achieve the planned Milestones / Deliverable or the need for a major change in their nature;
- major delay in providing contractual Reports or Deliverables;
- impossibility or clear irrelevance to maintain Work Packages or Tasks;
- major delay in starting or carrying out Work Packages or Tasks.

If a deviation from plan cannot be tackled by these means, or needs to be addressed before the updated implementation plan is in force, immediate corrective measures need to be taken. Whenever possible, such a deviation should be formalised in a recovery plan explaining the problem met, the consequences and impact on the project, actions to be taken to recover and any corresponding deadline. Such a recovery plan should normally be prepared and discussed within the PMT, and provided under the form of a PMT decision for the SC approval.

Several actions could then be envisaged and taken by the PMT / SC to palliate the problems arising from the difficulties encountered in the progress of the Project. Monitoring and follow-up of agreed mitigation measures and actions remain under the responsibility of the PC and the PMT.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This Project Management and Quality Plan sets out and defines the management structures, tools and processes, and the quality management system of the 5GMETA Project. In comparison with the previous version, in this document the management procedures have been revised and some new ones defined considering the feedback of the first project review. In addition, the 5GMETA communication and management tools have been described in more detail. The document includes specific information about 5GMETA, like the names of the members and the gender balance of governance bodies. The 5GMETA risk register can now be found as an Annex.

This report is complemented by the other deliverables in WP1, particularly D1.2 (Innovation plan) and D1.3 (Data management plan), as well as the communications plan of WP7.

Together with the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement, this document is to be regarded as a reference for the overall project management of 5GMETA, to ensure good organisation of work effort and high quality of Project results.

ANNEX 1: 5GMETA RISK REGISTER

Risk ID	WP	Risk Description <i>(The risk is that if...)</i>	Impact <i>(Then...)</i>	Impact level	Control / Mitigation <i>(How the risk is monitored & managed)</i>	Risk Owner <i>(organization)</i>	Initiation Date <i>(when it is identified)</i>	Trigger Date <i>(when it will occur)</i>	Probability	Probability	Probability	First Contingency Plan			
									original	current	target	Action ID	Action Description	Owner	Due Date
5GMETA.Risk01	1, 2	Discrepancies in the technical vision	Project delays, adjustment of contributions.	Medium	Frequent communication of WP leader and partners to solve minor issues to reach agreements and consensus. Coordinator sets deadlines to make decisions and to elevate to the Steering Committee persistent issues.	PC (VICOM)	1-Sep-2020		Low	Low	Low	5GMETA.Risk01_Act-1	Increase the number of face to face meetings. Project Management committee will take final decisions on any disagreements and monitor poor partner performance and any serious issue which may cause delays/failure. Partners will be replaced if necessary.	PC (VICOM)	
5GMETA.Risk02	2, 3, 4	Technical work diverges from project initial goals: Core technical items not adequately addressed to meet project objectives.	Project objectives are not completely met.	Medium	Incremental work phases. Fluent communication of WP Leaders with the Project Management Team and the Steering Committee, to detect minor deviation on an early stage. Agile methodology to align the overall goal and the iterations goals.	TC (VICOM)	1-Sep-2020		Low	Low	Low	5GMETA.Risk02_Act-1	Increase the number of face to face meetings. The TC will ensure that technological decisions/directions within the project keep aligned. When a partner does not meet the consortium's performance expectations, and following attempts to rectify the situation fail, they will be replaced by (preferably) a new group, department from within the existing consortium, or by a new partner.	TC (VICOM)	
5GMETA.Risk03	2, 6	5GMETA solution has not a flexible, modular and versatile design, not able to cover different business logics and use cases.	5GMETA solution constrained to few use cases and business models.	High	All the consortium partners are involved in WP2 and feedback from other stakeholders will be gathered (via hackathons on WP6). The interoperability and flexibility will be a key factor in the iterative design. The continuous activities on hackathons with incubators, clusters, SMEs and start-ups should widen the scope and applicability of the platform to heterogeneous services and applications with diverse business models in terms of SLAs and data licenses.	WP2L (LINKS)	1-Sep-2020		Medium	Medium	Low	5GMETA.Risk03_Act-1	The consortium will increase the number of face-to-face meetings to ensure that technological design is not fully tied to a single solution and cover all the needs from demonstrators.	WP2L (LINKS)	
5GMETA.Risk04	6	Interfaces for third-parties are not satisfying their needs or not accepted.	5GMETA platform's exploitation possibilities are reduced.	High	Consortium integrates players in all the automotive data value chain with different perspectives and exploitation models (academia, RTO, cluster, incubator, industry and SMEs) to create an interoperable solution, instead of an ad-hoc one. Activities on hackathons with incubators, clusters, SMEs and start-ups will widen the scope and applicability of the platform to heterogeneous services and apps with diverse business models, SLAs and data licenses.	WP6L (LIFTT)	1-Sep-2020		Medium	Medium	Low	5GMETA.Risk04_Act-1	The TC will ensure that technological decisions are not tied to a single solution suggesting alternative technologies.	TC (VICOM)	
5GMETA.Risk05	5	Not successful achieving the metrics (both frontend and backend) to measure the quality of the service.	The potential of 5GMETA's monitoring dashboard is dramatically reduced.	High	Resources platform utilization, data throughput, data singularity and license, geographic region, different cost/effective trade-offs and SLAs will be declared. Accountability of all these factors collected from distributed systems is visualized by the dashboard in a centralized server based on widely employed open source software technologies.	T5.3 Leader (AKKA)	1-Sep-2020		Low	Low	Low	5GMETA.Risk05_Act-1	Continuous communication with the 5GPPP Automotive WG and incubators, clusters, SMEs and start-ups by means of hackathons will help to create metrics accepted by stakeholders and newcomers to automotive ecosystem.	TC (VICOM)	

Figure 17 5GMETA Risk register's foreseen risks (part 1)

5GMETA.Risk06	4, 5	The 5GMETA demonstrators do not implement the new business logics adequately and do not satisfy needs from new automotive players or new markets.	The potential of 5GMETA platform is not sufficiently demonstrated.	Medium	According to the specification defined in WP2, and integrating the platform created through WP3 will be able to implement different use cases and business logics within the demonstrators developed in WP4 validated in WP5. The selection of representative use cases for a variety of customer segments and with different added value models will cover all business corners that will be validated by demonstrators. A wider applicability will be backed by the hackathons driven by incubators and clusters from the feedback captured from participant SMEs and start-ups.	WP4L (AKKA)	1-Sep-2020	Low	Low	Low	5GMETA.Risk06_Act-1	In cases where the project might seem to go off track, the WP4 will take immediate corrective action, which could include reducing functionality, changing partner budgets, changing leadership roles and so on.	WP4L (AKKA)
5GMETA.Risk07	5	Underestimation of the costs required for the deployment of demonstrators.	Increase of the project expenses.	Low	Consortium will estimate the infrastructure required for a set of use cases, representative for different customer segments and added value models. WINDTRE brings a 5G infrastructure to deploy Edge Network Functions of 5GMETA platform operating data pipelines, monitored and controlled by a central 5GMETA server for accountability and configuration. Servers providing services and apps will be provided by use case/demonstrator leaders invoking 5GMETA APIs.	WP5 Leader (ICOOR)	1-Sep-2020	Low	Low	Low	5GMETA.Risk07_Act-1	In each iteration the infrastructure scale will be updated. WP5 Leader and the SC will decide in case of an underestimation.	WP5L (ICOOR)
5GMETA.Risk08	6, 7	Dissemination, standardisation and exploitation of the product not successful.	Project does not reach dissemination, standardisation or market targets.	High	WP6 will actively focus on the identification of market audience and business models. The consortium includes organisations, well-positioned in the 5G and automotive fields with influence in standardisation bodies and in the sector.	WP7 Leader (ERT)	1-Sep-2020	Low	Low	Low	5GMETA.Risk08_Act-1	Special effort during the marketing and dissemination tasks will be carried out. Extra events and acts will be planned with stakeholders. For example, to ensure standardisation bodies approve our ideas continuous discussions and	WP7L (ERT)
5GMETA.Risk09	6, 7, 1	Conflicts of interest between partners on commercial model.	No agreement on commercial model.	High	All partners involved in 5GMETA are complementary; bringing in the project a specific expertise that none of the others could claim to have. There are very few overlaps in the core business activities of the consortium partners, reducing the risk of conflicts of interest.	T7.4 Leader (ICOOR)	1-Sep-2020	Low	Low	Low	5GMETA.Risk09_Act-1	WP6, WP7 and WP1 will activate the adequate mechanisms to protect IPR, to analyse the background and foreground provided by each one of the partners to the project, and to avoid conflicts.	T7.4 Leader (ICOOR)

Figure 18 5GMETA Risk register's foreseen risks (part 2)

Risk ID	WP	Risk Description (The risk is that if...)	Impact (Then...)	Impact level	Control / Mitigation (How the risk is monitored & managed)	Risk Owner	Initiation Date	Trigger Date	Probability	Probability	Probability	First Contingency Plan			Second Contingency Plan		
									original	current	target	Action ID	Action Description	Action Owner	Action ID	Action Description	Action Owner
5GMETA.Risk10	1, 4, 5, 6, 7	COVID-19 pandemic causes restrictions that affect mobility and/or gathering of people. Travelling might be limited, not recommended or forbidden between EU countries or even inside the same country. Public or private gatherings might be limited to a small number of people.	No face-to-face meetings. Delays on the deployment and roll-out of the solutions. Delay of deliverables and milestones.	Medium	The project has been extended 6 months to mitigate potential future restrictions. Regular updates from partners regarding measures in their country and updated estimates of roll-out. Tight coordination with the PO and the affected WP leaders. Use of software tools for remote collaborative work (chat, videoconferencing, file storage, etc).	PC (VICOM)	1-Sep-2020	1-Sep-2020	High	Medium	Low	5GMETA.Risk10_Act-1	Replace physical events (meetings, hackatons, ...) with virtual events.	PC (VICOM)	5GMETA.Risk10_Act-2	Ask for a project extension and a Grant Agreement Amendment to postpone the most affected deliverables and milestones.	SC
5GMETA.Risk11	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7	5G Network is scarcely deployed over pilot sites, or with limited 5G features	Limited demonstrations of 5G capabilities, and limited capabilities of 5GMETA platform.	High	Document the requirements of each demonstrator and the features of each pilot site to move a demonstrator to another pilot site if necessary. Make the demonstrators backwards compatible. Study the option of simulation to replace some 5G features.	WP4L (AKKA)	1-Oct-2021		Low	Low	Low	5GMETA.Risk11_Act-1	Move affected demonstrator to another pilot site that has the needed features.	WP4L (AKKA)	5GMETA.Risk11_Act-2	Replace the missing 5G features with simulation.	WP4L (AKKA)

Figure 19 5GMETA Risk register's unforeseen risks

Risk ID	Probability -->		Month	Month	Month	Month	Month	Month
	Original	Target	12	13	14	15	16	17
5GMETA.Risk01	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low			
5GMETA.Risk02	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low			
5GMETA.Risk03	Medium	Low	Medium	Medium	Medium			
5GMETA.Risk04	Medium	Low	Medium	Medium	Medium			
5GMETA.Risk05	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low			
5GMETA.Risk06	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low			
5GMETA.Risk07	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low			
5GMETA.Risk08	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low			
5GMETA.Risk09	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low			
5GMETA.Risk10	High	Low	Medium	Medium	Medium			
5GMETA.Risk11	Low	Low			Low			

Figure 20 5GMETA Risk register's risk record

